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Effect of 3d-Animation Illustration on Interest in Geometry Concept among Upper Basic Students in Federal Capital Territory, Abuja, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of 3D animation illustration on interest in geometry concept among upper basic in FCT. The effect of gender on the use of 3D animation illustration was also investigated. The study adopted a quasi- experimental pre-test, post-test control group design. The population of the study comprised of all the upper basic two (JSS 2) mathematics students, during the 2023/2024 academic session in Abuja. The sample of the study consist of 120 (Male 56 and Female 64) upper basic two (JSS 2) students selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique. The experimental group were taught geometry using 3D Animation Illustration (DAI) while the control group were taught using Conventional Teaching Method (CTM). Data were collected using Geometry Students Interest Inventory Scale (GSIIS). The instrument was validated by experts, and its reliability was assessed using Cronbach alpha, yielding a reliability index of 0.938. The data was analysed using mean rank to answer the research questions and Mann Whitney to test the hypotheses. The result from the analysis shows that there was significant differences in the mean rank of interest rating of students taught geometry using 3D animation illustration (DAI) and those taught with Conventional Teaching Methods (CTM) This study concluded based on the findings that the use of 3D animation illustration was effective for teaching geometry in mathematics for upper basic students. The study recommended among others that Government should provide training and professional development for teachers to effectively use 3D animation in their classrooms.

Keywords: 3D animation, geometry concept, interest in learning, educational technology, visual and interactive learning.

Introduction

Mathematics plays a key and fundamental role in the development and growth of any nation. Its significance lies in its necessity for scientific discoveries and technological breakthroughs, which are indicators of a developed economy (Anigbo, 2016). Research shows that mathematics is essential for achieving scientific and technological advancements, contributing to sustainable economic development in many nations (Gambari, Shittu, Daramola, & Jimoh, 2016). Science and technology are two distinct concepts that work in together, and mathematics serves as an essential instrument for achievements in both fields (Akinoso, 2011). Adigbo (2016) defined mathematics as the science of magnitude and number, highlighting its importance in virtually all subject areas. This is because all fields depend on it for problem-solving and predicting outcomes. He emphasized that competence in mathematics is crucial for individuals and nations alike, in areas such as domestic and business transactions, scientific discoveries, technological breakthroughs, problem-solving, and decision-making. Hom and Gordon (2021) assert that mathematics is fundamental to everything we do, forming the foundation for daily life, technology, architecture, art, finance, engineering, and even sports. They stressed that mathematical discoveries have been integral throughout history, evolving as society became more complex from basic counting to advanced calculations in modern civilizations.

Akinoso (2011) argued that mathematics is vital to science, technology, and economic development, particularly for underdeveloped nations. He stated that for countries like Nigeria to progress, they must enhance their science, technology, and

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economy through effective mathematics education. Gimba and Agwagah (2012) further noted that Nigeria relies heavily on science and technology to combat poverty, ignorance, and disease, which are key indicators of underdevelopment. Recognizing the critical importance of mathematics, the Federal Government of Nigeria made it a core, compulsory subject at all educational levels, as outlined in the National Policy on Education (FRN, 2014). This policy also mandates that students seeking admission to tertiary institutions must pass mathematics at a credit level. Despite the pivotal role of mathematics in economic development through science and technology, Odili (as cited in Safo, Ezenwa, & Wushishi, 2013) observed that many students view mathematics as difficult, which leads to a lack of interest. Students often struggle to retain what they've learned, largely due to the excessive use of theoretical explanations and formulas by teachers, while students remain passive listeners. According to Idigo (2010), the persistent poor performance in mathematics at Nigeria's primary and post-primary school levels is largely due to students' lack of interest, which is closely tied to their mastery of foundational skills. Mastery of junior secondary school (JSS) mathematics is crucial for success at the senior secondary school (SSS) level, and interest in the subject can strongly predict future success. Interest in mathematics, as noted by Idigo (2010) and Goolsby (2013), can be assessed to gauge a student's readiness for further study. Factors influencing students' lack of interest include math anxiety, classroom distractions, inadequate infrastructure, and ineffective instructional strategies (Akinoso, 2011; Goolsby, 2013; Anigbo, 2016), emphasized that a teacher's qualifications play a significant role in students' interest and success in mathematics. A well-qualified teacher can employ diverse teaching methods and materials, effectively engaging students and fostering a positive learning environment. Akinoso (2011) also underscored the importance of qualified mathematics teachers in enhancing students' interest in the subject. Effective teaching, grounded in diverse instructional strategies, can reduce students' anxiety about mathematics and improve their understanding. Teachers can also use math games and improvised materials to make learning more engaging. Goolsby (2013) highlighted factors such as attitudes toward success, confidence, teacher perceptions, and math anxiety as influential in students' interest in mathematics.

Geometry, defined by Oviawe and Uddin (2020) as the study of the size, shape, and position of 2D and 3D objects, is foundational to fields like engineering and technology (Giannakopoulos, 2017). Tieng and Eu (2014) emphasized the role of geometry in developing analytical and problem-solving skills, and Charles, Cyril, and Gierdien (2020) added that it fosters spatial intuition and deeper mathematical understanding. Despite its importance, the WAEC (2020) report revealed that students often avoid geometry-related questions. Russell (2018) argued that geometry builds crucial thinking skills like logic and deductive reasoning, suggesting it should be taught from primary school through university. However, students' poor performance in geometry is linked to factors such as weak foundational knowledge, lack of interest, and untrained teachers (Tsao, 2018). Dinayusadewi and Agustika (2020) noted challenges in teaching Euclidean geometry, including ineffective pedagogy and a lack of technology use in classrooms. Oviawe and Uddin (2020) emphasized the need for innovative teaching methods aligned with today's students' scientific literacy and technological fluency. Computers have been successfully used in developed countries to address teaching and learning challenges (Yusuf & Afolabi, 2010). Gambari, Ezenwa and Anyanwu (2014) added that Computer-Assisted Instruction can boost students' interest and achievement in mathematics through interactive lessons, animations, and immediate feedback. It can also be applied across various subjects, offering drills, tutorials, games, simulations, and animations to make learning more engaging and effective. Animation, as a form of visual information, can significantly enhance learning. Gambari, Falode, and Adegbenro (2014) distinguished between static and animated illustrations, with the latter showing processes in operation, making learning more interactive. Justin (2020) defined animation as images in motion, highlighting its potential to enliven learning, increase engagement, and enhance students' motivation. According to Gambari, Falode and Adegbenro (2014), animation effectively integrates visual and verbal information, allowing for better retention in long-term memory and improving recall and problem-solving skills. Studies by Westhof, Bergman, and Carroll (2010), as well as Karacop and Doymus (2013), supported the idea that computer animations enhance academic performance, especially in subjects like biology, chemistry, and mathematics. Regarding gender differences in mathematics interest, research findings are mixed. Unodiaku (2013) reported that male students generally outperformed females, while other studies, such as Chikendu (2018) found that female students had a higher interest than their male counterparts. However, Iwendi (2012), Achor, Imoko and Ajai (2010), Ojo (2022) and Njoku and Okigbo (2021) found no significant effect of gender on students' interest scores in geometry and mathematics performance in general. Given the importance of geometry in education and the challenges students face in learning it, particularly in Nigeria, exploring effective teaching methods is essential. The literature reviewed indicates limited research on the use of 3D animation in teaching mathematics, especially geometry, at the junior secondary school level in the FCT. This study aimed to assess the impact of 3D animation illustrations on students' interest in geometry. The unique features of 3D animation such as visualizing 3D objects, facilitating self-paced learning, providing positive reinforcement, and offering immediate feedback make it a promising tool for enhancing geometry learning.

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Statement of the Research Problem

Geometry at the junior secondary school level forms the basis for more advanced mathematical concepts, but it is often challenging for students. In the 2024 WASSCE, while 72.12% of candidates earned credits in five subjects, many struggled with geometry, particularly in understanding theorems, properties of shapes and their practical applications, leading to poor performance in this area (Daily Trust, 2024). The conventional teaching methods for geometry often rely on static 2D illustrations and abstract explanations, which can hinder students' ability to visualize and comprehend complex geometric concepts. Consequently, many students find it difficult to engage with the subject, resulting in low levels of interest. Recent technological advancements have introduced 3D animation as a potential tool to enhance teaching and learning by providing dynamic, interactive visual representations of geometric shapes and principles. However, despite the increasing popularity of 3D animation in education, there is limited empirical evidence regarding its effectiveness in improving students' interest in geometry, particularly at the junior secondary school level in the FCT, Abuja. This study sought to address this gap by investigating the impact of 3D animation illustrations on the interest of junior secondary school students in geometry. By comparing the outcomes of students taught with 3D animation to those taught using conventional methods, this research aimed to determine whether the integration of 3D animation can enhance student engagement in geometry.

Purpose of the study

This study investigated the effect of 3D animation illustrations on interest in geometry concept among upper basic students in FCT Abuja, Nigeria. The study therefore, investigated the following objectives:

1. The effect of 3D animation illustration on interest in geometry concepts among upper basic class two students in FCT.
2. The influence of gender on interest in geometry concepts among upper basic class two students taught 3D animations illustration in FCT.

Research questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study.

1. What is the difference in the mean rank interest rating of students taught geometry using 3D animation illustrations (DAI) and those taught using conventional teaching method (CTM)
2. What is the difference in the mean rank interest rating of male and female students taught geometry using 3D animation illustration (DAI)

Research Hypotheses

The following null Hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significant level:

H₁: There is no significant difference in the mean rank interest rating of students taught geometry using 3D animation illustrations (DAI) and those taught geometry using conventional teaching method (CTM).

H₂: There is no significant difference in the mean rank interest rating of male and female students taught geometry using 3D animation illustration (DAI)

Methodology

The study adopted a quasi-experimental pre-test, post-test control group design. The population of the study comprised of all the upper basic two (JSS 2) mathematics students, during the 2023/2024 academic session in Abuja. The sample of the study consist of 120 (Male 56 and Female 64) upper basic two (JSS 2) students selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique. Upper basic two (JSS2) was selected using purposive sampling techniques. Two schools were selected out of 20 upper basic two in Gwagwalada area council for this study, which include experimental and control group. The experimental school was selected using purposive sampling techniques due to the fact that the school has solar system, and computer laboratory. The control group school was selected by simple random sampling. A total of 120 students were used on two intact classes, one from each school selected. This was to avoid the disruption of the school programmes. The schools selected were JSS Phase 3 Gwagwalada assigned to experimental group A and JSS Dukpa assigned to control group B. The experimental group A (JSS Phase 3 Gwagwalada) comprises of 30 male and 40 female out of about 626 students (male 306 and female 320) and the control group B (JSS Dukpa) comprises of 26 male and 24 female out of about 164 students (male 89 and female 75).

The data were collected using Geometry Students Interest Inventory Scale (GSIIS). A Geometry Student's Interest inventory scale consisted of 20 items, which was used to measure the influence of teaching method on students' interest in geometry. The students were instructed to place a tick (✓) in the column which best indicate their opinion on a modified 4-

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point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (1), Agree (2) in positive statements to Strongly Disagree (3), Disagree (4) in negative statements. The students' score determined the sum of the weight of the alternatives the student had chosen or selected.

The instrument was then summited alongside the lesson plan to experts in science and environmental education department for face and content validation. In order to assess the reliability of the instrument, the study was subjected to trial testing. Twenty (20) students were drawn randomly from a school not included in the study population. The students were distributed into two classes of 10 students each. It was believed that they had prior knowledge of the subject matter, as they were not exposed to any intervention before the instrument was administered on them. The test was administered in one day and they were retested after a week without creating any awareness of retest. The result obtained were compared for correlation. The Cronbach's Alpha was used to assess the correlation with combined total across both parts as: 0.938. The result of the test indicated a high level of internal consistency and reliability. This implied that the instrument was reliable and stable. The GeoGebra calculator suite was used to displayed the various geometry animations.

Figure 1

Different lesson plans were prepared on the topics: Solid shapes (cube, cylinder and cone) using the two teaching methods; 3D Animation illustrations and the conventional teaching method. A Mathematics class teacher from each school selected was trained on the procedure as a research assistance. The Geometry Students Interest Inventory Scale (GSIS) was administered as a pre test before the start of the experiment to determine the initial level of interest students had in geometry, after which the experiment begins. The experimental group was taught geometry using 3D Animation illustrations with laptop and projector since there're no computer available for the students in public schools in FCT and Gwagwalada Area Council in particular. GeoGebra calculator suite was used for animation demonstration. The control group was then taught geometry using conventional teaching method, that's lecture method, after which GSIS was administered as a post test to find out to what extent students' interest had been influenced by the treatment. These procedures lasted for four (4) weeks.

The data collected were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23. Mean rank was used to answer the research questions while, Mann Whitney U Test was used to test the hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05.

Findings

Research Question 1:

What is the difference in the mean rank of interest rating of students taught geometry using 3D animation illustrations (DAI) and those taught using conventional teaching method (CTM)

Table 2: Mean Rank of Interest Rating Scores of Students Taught Geometry Using 3D Animation Illustrations (DAI) and Those Taught Using Conventional Teaching Method (CTM)

Group	N	Mean Rank
DAI	70	67.76
CTM	50	50.33
Mean rank difference		17.43

Table 2 shows the mean rank of interest rating scores of students taught geometry using 3D animation illustrations (DAI) and those taught using conventional teaching method (CTM). From the results obtained, students taught geometry using DAI had a mean rank of interest rating score of 67.76 while the students taught geometry using CTM had a mean rank of interest rating score of 50.33. Therefore, the mean rank difference in interest rating scores between students taught geometry using DAI and those taught geometry using CTM is 17.43 in favour of students in DAI group.

Research Question 2:

What is the difference in the mean rank of interest rating of male and female students taught geometry using 3D animation illustration (DAI)?

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Table 3: Mean Rank of Interest Rating of Male and Female Students Taught Geometry Using 3D Animation Illustration (DAI)

Group	Gender	N	Mean Rank
DAI	Female	40	37.75
	Male	30	32.50
Mean rank difference			5.25

Table 3 shows the mean rank of male and female students of 3D animation illustration (DAI) group with respect to their interest rating in geometry. From the results obtained, female students had a mean rank interest rating score of 37.75 while the male students had a mean rank interest rating of 32.50. Therefore, the mean rank difference in interest rating between male and female students in DAI group is 5.25 in favour of female students.

Testing of the Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean rank of interest rating of students taught geometry using 3D animation illustrations (DAI) and those taught geometry using conventional teaching method (CTM).

Table 4: Summary of Mann Whitney Results of Interest Rating of Students Taught Geometry Using 3D Animation Illustrations (DAI) and Those Taught Geometry Using Conventional Teaching Method (CTM)

Group	N	Sum of Ranks	Mann Whitney U	Z	Sig@0.05	Remark
DAI	70	4743.50	1241.50	2.788	0.005	Significant
TTM	50	2516.50				

From Table 4 results of the Mann Whitney nonparametric test shows that the computed sum of ranks scores are 4743.50 and 2516.50 by DAI and CTM groups respectively. The computed Mann Whitney U value of 1241.50 is higher than the 2.788 Z scores. The calculated p-value of 0.005 is less than the 0.05 level of significant. This implies that the mean rank interest development of DAI and CTM groups is significantly different when both groups are taught Geometry. Consequently, hypothesis one which states that there is no significant difference in the mean rank of interest rating of students taught geometry using 3D animation illustrations (DAI) and those taught geometry using conventional teaching method (CTM), is hereby rejected.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean rank of interest rating of male and female students taught geometry using 3D animation illustration (DAI).

Table 5: Summary of Mann Whitney Results of Interest Rating of Male and Female Students Taught Geometry Using 3D Animation Illustration (DAI)

Gender	N	Sum of Ranks	Mann Whitney U	Z	Sig@0.05	Remark
Female	40	1510.00	510.000	1.177	0.239	Not Significant
Male	30	975.00				

From Table 5 results of the Mann Whitney nonparametric test shows that the computed sum of ranks scores are 1510.00 and 975.00 by female and male respectively. The computed Mann Whitney U value is 510.000 and the Z score is 1.177. The calculated p-value of 0.239 is greater than the 0.05 level of significant. This implies that the mean rank interest development by female and male students in DAI group is not significantly different when both genders are taught Geometry using DAI. Consequently, hypothesis two which states that there is no significant difference in the mean rank of interest rating of male and female students taught geometry using 3D animation illustration (DAI), is hereby accepted.

Discussion of findings.

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Based on the findings of the data analysis, hypothesis one revealed that, there were significant difference in interest rating of students taught geometry using DAI and those taught with CTM in favour of those in DAI group. This finding is in line with the finding of Tepla, Teply and Smejkal (2022) whose study revealed that using 3D models and animations in the teaching process significantly increase students' interest in learning natural sciences. This was supported by Njoku and Okigbo (2021) who reported that, the students taught geometry using GeoTAN instructional software package (GISP) have higher mean interest score in geometry than those taught with conventional method.

Hypothesis two revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean rank of interest rating of male and female students exposed to DAI. This finding is in agreement with the findings of Achor, Imoko and Ajai (2010) who reported that there was no significant difference in the mean interest rating of male and female students taught geometry using games and simulation. This was contrary to the findings of Allahnana, Akande, Vintseh, Alaku and Alaku (2018) and Unodiaku (2013), whose study revealed that male students excel in Mathematics more than their female counterparts. Also, male students have interest in Mathematics more than the female students. Other findings show that female students are better in mathematics interest such as the study of chikendu (2018), reported that instructional computer animation had a significant effect on students' interest in chemistry. Female students performed better than the Male students taught using instructional computer animation.

Conclusion

The use of 3D animation illustration was found to be effective for teaching concepts of geometry in mathematics for junior secondary school students. It enhanced students' interest in geometry. It also gives equal learning opportunities to both male and female students in geometry.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Schools and educators should incorporate 3D Animation Illustrations (DAI) into their teaching methods to increase student interest and engagement in geometry. This approach has shown to significantly boost interest compared to conventional methods.
2. Although no significant differences in interest ratings were observed between male and female students using DAI, it's essential to continue monitoring and analyzing these dynamics. Ensuring that teaching methods cater effectively to all genders could help maintain equitable learning outcomes.

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